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REGULATION OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE REGION IS AN EXAMPLE OF RUSSIA

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РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ЗАНЯТОСТИ В РЕГИОНЕ ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ ПРИМЕРОМ РОССИИ

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ROSSIYA MISOLIDA MINTAQADA BANDLIKNI TARTIBGA SOLISH

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abstract

In our scientific article, we study the experiences and methods of various developed countries in regulating employment, assisting it, and reducing the unemployment rate, and we think about achieving good results if we apply these experiences in our country.

аннотация

В нашей научной статье мы изучаем опыт и методы различных развитых стран в регулировании занятости, содействии ей и снижении уровня безработицы и думаем о достижении хороших результатов, если применим этот опыт в нашей стране.

annotatsiya

ilmiy maqolamizda biz turli rivojlangan mamlakatlarning bandlikni tartibga solish, unga yordam berish va ihsizlik darajasini pasaytirish

bo'yicha tajribalari va usullarini o'rganamiz va agar biz ushbu tajribalarni mamlakatimizda qo'llasak, yaxshi natijalarga erishish haqida o'ylashimiz mumkin.

Keywords:

Conceptual approach, state employment policy, transfer payments.

Ключевые слова:

концептуальный подход, государственная политика занятости, трансфертные выплаты.

Kalit so'zlar:

kontseptual yondashuv, davlat bandlik siyosati, transfer to'lovlari.

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In this article, we will familiarize yourself below with the measures, programs, recommended methodologies developed by the state in the field of employment assistance and regulation of the Russian Federation – the region, reducing the unemployment rate:

1. On the basis of a critical study of literary sources, the methodological limitations of the existing conceptual approaches to the state policy on the regulation of population employment are determined, their connection with the specific historical nature, the specific state of the economy, and the national characteristics of a certain period is determined. The time point is emphasized, which does not allow us to talk about the possibility of developing a unified theory of state regulation of employment.

2. Currently, great attention is paid to the role of regions in the implementation of the state employment policy;

key priorities are highlighted;

the possibilities of the regions are being considered.

Regulatory instruments at the regional level: income, transfer payments, financial and credit instruments within local and regional budgets, housing and industrial construction programs, state purchase of enterprise products; providing targeted subsidies, loans and tax breaks to enterprises (regional taxes). Supporting small businesses at the regional level, self-employment, development of production in priority sectors, information provision, improvement of the structure of regulatory bodies, improvement of employment efficiency, training and retraining of the workforce measures to develop systems, improve social support for the unemployed are more effective at the national level. The regional level of labor market regulation, unlike the state level, takes into account local characteristics.

3. As a result of transferring the issue of employment to the regional level, there is a need to develop the theoretical aspects of regional regulation of employment;

In justifying the scientific and practical recommendations on the improvement of regulatory methods, as well as the system of effective sanctions;

In formulating a strategy for increasing employment in the region. It is necessary to clarify the mechanism of financing measures for the preservation and creation of additional jobs.

At the level of practical activity, there is a problem of distribution of powers and functions between federal, regional and local government bodies, in which a situation of dual subordination is possible. Also, the question of adequacy of funding sources for regional employment programs remains important; adaptation of financial and credit tools of employment regulation to regional conditions; formation of tactical and strategic goals and objectives of employment policy in relation to regional characteristics; development of a spectrum of employment regulation institutions,

mechanisms and procedures. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the modern tendency to increase the demands of the economic entity of employers in a tough competitive environment with high production and economic mobility, while maintaining a low level of real wages. In this regard, it is necessary to look for and create conditions for the development of quality jobs in the region, which will allow a person to realize his personal interest, achieve high labor productivity and have a decent income that guarantees the normal reproduction of the employee and his family.

4. The existing system of state regulation of the labor market at the regional level is not effective, but a number of actions to increase it have already been implemented: a set of measures to form a single right-wing space of the country has been implemented, the center and regions are the delimitation of the powers between the governments was completed, the system of inter-budgetary relations was improved, and the first stage of the administrative reform was completed. the new structure of federal authorities and their relations with the state authorities of constituent entities of the Russian Federation. In addition, it is necessary to strengthen the existing factors of increasing employment, which affect the increase in the demand for labor force; to distinguish actions that can be implemented at the expense of administrative and financial resources of a number of sources, to develop principles, methods, strategy and monitoring elements for evaluating the effectiveness of programs.

5. The leading elements of employment policy formation in the region can be:

- Mechanisms to maintain existing jobs and create new (additional) jobs in the region by forming the financial attractiveness of business. It is based on the principle of investment attractiveness, taking into account cross-sectoral relations and regional aspects;

- Expanding social partnership and improving the strategy of increasing employment in the region, taking into account the specific characteristics of the requirements of employers with existing personnel potential;

- Stimulation of small business development as a leading factor in ensuring employment in the labor market. The main task is to help create more quality jobs in the small business sector.

6. Creation of additional jobs in the region is proposed by forming the financial attractiveness of business. The way out of the lack of effective demand for labor force is to increase public spending on employment policy and look for other sources of financing. To develop production, the public investment system should focus on "modernization" capital investments: This means prioritizing capital investments for modernization rather than new construction. Technical re-equipment of the existing production is possible, it can be expanded to the required level. The process of creating jobs should include a list of solutions: choosing the area where jobs will be created in

the future; calculation of conjugation coefficients and costs of creation and maintenance of jobs by industries, calculation of socio-economic efficiency.

7. Expanding social partnership and improving the strategy of increasing employment in the region, taking into account the specific characteristics of the requests of employers with existing personnel potential:

- Organization of entrepreneurs' associations and expansion of trade union activities as a strategic goal;

- Improving the mechanisms for protecting the labor rights of employees, including the formation of the institution of trade unions and encouraging entrepreneurs to provide some economic benefits and employment guarantees to the most qualified workers;

- State support for the development of the system of mutual cooperation of the participants of "Extended social partnership";

By creating a spectrum of institutions, mechanisms and procedures of social communication, an effective system of sanctions.

The province requires the development of a compensation mechanism for the creation and maintenance of jobs by employers at the expense of the regional and local budget.

8. Improvement of the state policy on small business support from the point of view of employment expansion is possible by encouraging self-employment and small business development as a leading factor in ensuring employment in the labor market. The main task is to help create more quality jobs in the small business sector. Implementation of organizational and economic activities is possible by combining small and large businesses and ensuring an increase in the number of self-employed people.

9. Dissertation studies allow us to conclude that a necessary condition for regulating employment at the regional level is the development of a system of mutual relations between regional employment bodies, municipalities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation and business. It is proposed to increase the efficiency of the state apparatus through the development of inter-budgetary relations, the implementation of state investments for the development of production in order to stimulate the employment of the population, etc.

Based on the above, we hope that it will not be without benefits if it is used as a significant experiment in reducing unemployment and supporting employment in our country.

A new scheme for organizing the joint work of authorities and business in the development and implementation of the program is necessary; clearly defining the interests and priorities of the policy. It is appropriate to attract funds and business

development centers to the activities of PEC (Population Employment Centers) within the framework of creating additional jobs. It is necessary to improve the strategy of increasing employment in the region, taking into account the specific characteristics of the requests of employers with existing personnel potential.

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